

An Integrated Digital System for Managing and Maintaining ITS Equipment in Cyprus

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Abstract

This paper introduces an integrated system for managing and maintaining Intelligent Transport System (ITS) equipment. This service features a user-friendly mobile application, enabling maintenance operators (contractors) to access ITS device information and record both preventive and corrective maintenance activities. Additionally, a desktop application is provided for the Cyprus Road Authority (the contracting authority) to review detailed device information and maintenance history. Among the key benefits of this service, are the elimination of manual data entry, which reduces errors and enhances accuracy. By digitizing data collection and enabling real-time access to information, the system streamlines processes, making internal procedures smoother and faster. This seamless operation improves both accountability and productivity, allowing users to instantly access and retrieve updates or changes. It also increases the efficiency and sustainability of contractors' services while providing the contracting authority with enhanced monitoring capabilities for better oversight of maintenance procedures. Beyond these advantages, the system actively supports resilient and safe mobility by ensuring the continuous and reliable operation of ITS equipment. This reliability reduces the risk of disruptions in transportation networks, enhancing the safety and efficiency of mobility for all users. The system's ability to maintain an accurate asset register further facilitates proactive planning, ensuring equipment readiness and adaptability to changing mobility demands. Ultimately, the system empowers stakeholders to make faster, more informed decisions, significantly contributing to the modernization, sustainability, and resilience of ITS equipment management.

Keywords:

GIS, ITS Directive, ITS, ITS Equipment Maintenance, Digital Transformation, Cyprus

Introduction

Constant technological developments and industrial competitiveness create the necessity to adapt to these new states and to evolve into a new era. This era, characterized by connectivity, customization, and inventory reduction, has emerged [1,2]. This development is strongly associated with the integration between physical and digital systems of production environments [3]. The integration of these environments allows the collection of a large amount of data that is collected by different devices such as Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS)

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equipment. The above-mentioned factors have a strong relationship with maintenance procedures, which are crucial for the operation time and efficiency of equipment. Therefore, equipment faults need to be identified, solved, to prevent or minimize downtimes outages caused by both conventional and unconventional failures [3]. Such outages result in unexpected financial costs, either due to the need for removal of the device or the interruption in data collection [4].

In literature, different nomenclature and groups of maintenance management strategies can be found [1–4], classified as follows: 1) Corrective Maintenance: This is performed only in response to an operational failure of the equipment; 2) Preventive Maintenance: This is carried out periodically to anticipate equipment failures; while it is an effective approach to avoiding technical failures, it often leads to unnecessary corrective actions, increasing operating costs; and 3) Predictive Maintenance: This strategy utilizes predictive tools to determinate when maintenance actions are necessary. It relies on the continuous monitoring of a device, allowing maintenance to be performed only when needed. Furthermore, it enables the early detection of failures based on historical data, integrity factors and engineering approaches such as big data analytics, machine learning and artificial intelligence.

Some studies highlight significant advancements in digital twin frameworks to enhance maintenance operations, leveraging real-time data and simulations for optimized decision-making [5,6], while others [7] emphasize the importance of modeling and simulating ITS maintenance processes to improve the overall reliability of transportation systems. AI-driven predictive maintenance in smart transportation systems is the focus of [8], advocating for the integration of AI to enable proactive maintenance strategies. Additionally, [9] explore the impact of training on maintenance practices and overall equipment effectiveness, and [2] highlight the role of preventive maintenance management in the energy sector, offering insights applicable to transportation systems. In Cyprus, the Public Works Department (PWD) of the Ministry of Transport, Communications and Works of Cyprus (MTCW) is the authority responsible for installing new ITS-related equipment and ensuring its seamless operation and efficiency. However, the current system for managing and maintaining ITS equipment faces significant challenges that undermine its effectiveness. Information collection is still conducted manually using physical forms, making data management cumbersome and inefficient. Additionally, incomplete descriptive details of the installed equipment create gaps in understanding its overall status, while the lack of sufficient digital information further complicates data analysis and management. The absence of a standardized maintenance and inspection process results in inconsistent or missed checks, jeopardizing equipment reliability. Another key limitation is the inability to accurately identify the spatial locations of installed equipment, which hampers efforts to monitor and manage assets effectively. This issue is exacerbated by the lack of a robust mechanism to verify and control the costs of work performed by contractors, raising concerns about accountability and transparency. Finally, the current processes are time-consuming, causing delays in critical activities such as maintenance, reporting, and issue resolution.

In this context, and to address these challenges, an integrated system named EquipMaint (short for Equipment Maintenance) has been developed to streamline processes through two main components: a Mobile Application and a Desktop Application. The *Mobile Application* enables the maintenance operator (contractor) to access all relevant information about an installed ITS device directly from the field. Through a predefined control checklist,

the operator can report both preventive and corrective maintenance activities. Furthermore, the mobile application provides functionality to reallocate, disconnect, or decommission existing devices, ensuring seamless field operations. On the other hand, the *Desktop Application* is designed as an asset management tool for the contracting authority. It facilitates monitoring of the maintenance process and ensures that the contractor fulfills the requirements outlined in their concession contract, particularly regarding the quality of services provided for ITS equipment maintenance. Together, these applications enhance efficiency, improve data management, and ensure transparency and accountability in ITS equipment maintenance.

Objective

The main objectives of this paper are to 1) Showcase the EquipMaint service and its robust approach to managing and maintaining ITS-related equipment, 2) Illustrate how open-source components can be effectively integrated to deliver a complete and efficient solution for digital transformation in maintenance processes, 3) Emphasize the role of digital technologies in enhancing the monitoring and maintenance of ITS equipment, improving accuracy, and minimizing manual errors, 4) Demonstrate how the EquipMaint service can serve as a scalable and customizable solution for other entities aiming to implement efficient ITS equipment management and maintenance systems, and 5) Highlight its contribution to fostering resilient and safe mobility by ensuring that ITS equipment remains functional, reliable, and capable of supporting uninterrupted and secure transportation networks.

Background

PWD, in its efforts to comply with the ITS Directive 2010/40/EU [10] which is now amended by 2023/2661 [11], to deliver a safer road network, and deliver advanced ITS to its citizens, is closely collaborating with KIOS Research and Innovation Centre of Excellence (KIOS CoE) at the University of Cyprus, on several ITS initiatives. Among them is the development and implementation of a comprehensive Geographical Information System (GIS) known as the GNOSIS platform [12]. The developed platform, aims to facilitate the implementation of ITS across Cyprus and serves as the primary GIS system for managing the Cypriot primary road network, including its ITS equipment, road furniture and regulations. GNOSIS platform will be the backbone of a country wide level Digital Twin focusing on the primary road network and its associate elements. This will enable enhanced mobility management in all urban areas and the Cyprus TEN-T Network [13]. In this context, the overall objective of PWD is to install in the near future and integrate with the National Mobility Platform (NMP) and maintain approximately 400 road field ITS devices for the expansion of the NMP and the Cyprus National Access Point² (CyNAP). This aims to achieve an overall coverage of the primary urban and suburban road network of Cyprus and deliver the appropriate information to the managing authorities and the network's users. The field devices include induction loop traffic counters; weigh in motion loop traffic counters; Bluetooth detection devices; CCTV cameras (Pan-Tilt-Zoom); parking entrance loop vehicle counters; parking LED displays, and Variable Message Signs (VMS). For this purpose, it is of paramount importance to develop a digital infrastructure for the management and maintenance of ITS-related equipment.

² <https://www.traffic4cyprus.org.cy/map>

Method

An integrated methodology approach has been chosen to follow the progression of the phases of the system development and implementation through the system development life cycle. A hybrid version of Agile and Waterfall frameworks [14,15] has been selected, leveraging the best elements of both models into the development process [12,15]. The developed system is complying with IEEE standards (ISO/IEC/IEEE 29148:2018 - Systems and Software Engineering - Life Cycle Processes - Requirements Engineering) as a guide to identify the processes and products related to the requirements collection for the system throughout the life cycle of the project [16]. Security is an essential part of the system following the Information technology - Security techniques - Information security management systems (ISO/IEC 27000:2018; ISO/IEC 27001:2013 including Cor 1:2014 and Cor 2:2015; ISO/IEC 27002:2013 including Cor 1:2014 and Cor 2:2015) [17,18].

System Architecture

The EquipMaint service, aims to assist the stakeholders (PWD) in managing the installed road field ITS devices and monitoring the maintenance procedure from contractors. It validates whether the contractors fulfil the minimum requirements as stated in their concession contract with the public sector. In a nutshell, the contractors may use a mobile application pre-installed on their Android devices provided by the contracting authority. This allows them to easily access equipment information and perform, periodic preventive or corrective maintenance through a predefined checklist. Simultaneously, they can upload all necessary information for approval from the stakeholders. In addition, the contractor's personnel have the capability to change the location of an installed equipment or disconnect and decommission a device that is no longer functional. Every functionality of the application requires an initial QR code scan, placed on each equipment, to log the geographic location of the issue accurately. The reports submitted by the contractor, pertaining to any type of maintenance, are then evaluated from an authorized user from PWD through a desktop application. The authorized user can accept or reject the reports accordingly. In any case, the contractor remains in the loop through the status of their maintenance report, which is updated within the mobile application to reflect the progress.

The EquipMaint system is integrated with the GNOSIS ecosystem and consists of 3 functional components, as shown in Figure 1:

1. **Graphical User Interface (GUI):** The user interface of the EquipMaint service that consists of the views of the mobile application and the desktop counterpart. Both were designed, planned, and implemented to ensure the best end-user experience. The mobile application serves as a complementary tool to the desktop application in managing equipment. The open-source React-Native Framework, created by Meta Platforms, was adopted as the industry standard approach offering solutions to the challenges experienced by native application developers. This framework eases the development of the mobile app because it contains a collection of customizable and production-ready components written with the JavaScript programming language and, tools that help with the generation of native code and executable for Android [19]. The desktop application was developed as a specialized toolset using Python programming language and expanding that way the functionalities of the GNOSIS platform.

2. **Application Servers (AS):** The GNOSIS desktop and EquipMaint mobile applications run on dedicated servers that manage all functionalities and communicate with the database and external interfaces. Authentication services handle identity and access management, ensuring only authorized users can access specific features. Both applications are built using the Django web framework, which manages authentication, APIs, and integrates security features to guard against common vulnerabilities. The system uses a PostgreSQL database with efficient querying and employs the django-pgcrypto package to encrypt data transfers between application and database servers using PGP symmetric encryption. Robust security is enforced through encrypted communications, secure data storage, role-based access, two-factor authentication, detailed audit logging, and regular security audits, ensuring compliance with GDPR and related standards.
3. **Database Server (DBS):** The server that runs the EquipMaint database for handling the user data and application data. It is based on the object-relational database system of PostgreSQL with the PGCrypto extension, where the collected data and the maintenance information along with the access and change logs are stored and encrypted. At this level, the system stores all the gathered information to perform queries regarding maintenance or relevant invoice information.

Figure 1 –EquipMaint service through GNOSIS ecosystem

Results and Evaluation

Mobile Application

The EquipMaint mobile application features a user-friendly interface providing smart solutions and functions, as shown in Figure 2. Once contractor users are verified and logged-in (Figure 2a), they can create a maintenance report or browse the history of submitted reports (Figure 2b). To create a new report, users scan the self-adhesive QR code on the equipment, which automatically geotags the location to verify their presence in the field. This provides access to all relevant equipment details, and users can choose between preventive or corrective

maintenance (Figure 2d). Periodic preventing maintenance represents planned maintenance actions from the contractor, as stated in their concession contract with the public sector, occurring every six months. During this report, the contractor can maintain a high-level record (yes or no) through pre-defined control fields concerning the functional check of the installed sensor, the periodic diagnostic check and repair or replacement of corrupted parts. Corrective maintenance on the other hand, occurs every time that a device presents an operational failure. These breakdowns are mostly detected through the system of data monitoring, indicating whether a sensor has lost connection signal or not. Throughout this procedure, the user can maintain records and information about the elements of the sensor like SIM card number, battery serial number, wiring condition, and other components. In any case, additional comments, photos, and an invoice number can also be provided for evaluation. Moreover, the application allows users to reallocate devices by clearing the current location, rescanning the QR code, and updating the new coordinates, while maintaining a log of location history. If a device is unrepairable, users can disconnect it, clear its location, and mark it as destroyed, retaining its maintenance and location history. Navigating back to the home screen (Figure 2b), the user can switch to the report history to scroll through past maintenances and check the status of each report. The status of a report can be: (a) submitted, for a report that is submitted from the user for evaluation with all mandatory control fields completed, (b) pending, for a report that requires an invoice number to be provided from the contractor, (c) rejected, for reports where the contracting authority needs more clarifications about the services provided, and (d) accepted, for reports where the stakeholder will proceed with the invoice payment. Corresponding details of a report are displayed upon clicking on a specific one from the report list (Figure 2d-e).

Figure 2 - The user interface of the EquipMaint mobile application

This streamlined process is a strong aspect that has made internal procedures smoother and faster. As a result, both accountability and productivity have increased. The system's efficiency is further enhanced by enabling all users to simultaneously access the same information, allowing for instant retrieval of updates or changes. This solution aligns with the paperless office effort by eliminating the need for manual data entry back at the office, avoiding duplication of work, and minimizing errors, ultimately reducing operational costs. Consequently, contractor users can register or update field information, capture relevant data on the status of installed equipment, perform inventory management, collect maintenance details, and build an accurate asset

registry. With more precise asset data available, contractors can better plan future maintenance, enabling quicker and more informed decision-making.

Desktop Application

The desktop application serves as an additional toolkit, enhancing the functionalities of the GNOSIS platform, widely used by PWD in recent years. Through the application (Figure 3), authorized users from the contracting authority can visualize or edit all relevant information regarding an installed ITS device. Users can interact with the map to select a device or search by criteria such as equipment type, sub-type, or installation location. Each device has a unique QR-code identifier, which can be regenerated if the printed self-adhesive QR-code is destroyed. Upon selecting a device, users can access its maintenance history, associated documentation, and submitted reports. Subsequently, from this panel, the user can review all submitted reports and either reject or accept them upon a scheduled on-site inspection, if needed. For instance, a report may be rejected if the provided services are not satisfactory and, in this case, it will appear back to the contractor through the mobile application for re-evaluation. On the other hand, the user may accept a report by updating its status, triggering the status change within the mobile application. In this case, the invoice documentation requested from the contractor is necessary to proceed with any internal procedures for payment, and the final documentation must be uploaded to the system for future reference to maintain a payment record.

An additional element of this toolkit ecosystem is the ability of the user to submit a new device to the database with all corresponding technical information. Thus, the user can submit more than one entry in the system, generating their unique QR-code identifier at the same time. While these entries lack spatial information initially, it is assigned automatically during installation after scanning the QR-code through the mobile application. A follow-up on-site inspection by PWD personnel confirms the installation and finalizes the device's record. For all aforementioned step-by-step usage scenarios, PWD officers have greatly benefited from the use of the desktop application throughout the processing pipeline. Notably, there has been a significant increase in productivity and accountability at the departmental level. Errors in data collection, information management, maintenance monitoring, report storage, and payments have been minimized, leading to a substantial improvement in internal processes.

Figure 3 - The user interface of the EquipMaint toolkit through GNOSIS platform

Conclusions

This paper presented the design and implementation of the EquipMaint service, a robust solution for managing and maintaining ITS-related equipment. By leveraging open-source components and integrating innovative digital tools, the system provides a comprehensive, scalable, and customizable approach to modernizing ITS maintenance processes. The major findings can be summarized as follows: First, the EquipMaint service streamlines maintenance operations through its mobile and desktop applications, enhancing efficiency, accuracy, and transparency in managing ITS equipment. Second, the integration of open-source components, such as React-Native and Django, ensures a flexible and cost-effective solution for digital transformation, facilitating real-time monitoring and decision-making. Third, this service significantly reduces manual errors and operational costs through automated data collection and reporting, thereby improving productivity and enabling better asset management. Finally, its scalability and adaptable architecture make the system transferable to other entities or regions seeking to implement efficient ITS equipment management and maintenance solutions.

The EquipMaint digitization efforts align with modern infrastructure management requirements, supporting the creation of an accurate asset registry and facilitating better planning of future maintenance. Additionally, this initiative marks a significant step in the digital transformation of ITS infrastructure, fostering smarter and more sustainable operations. By improving internal processes, increasing accountability, and enabling real-time decision-making, the EquipMaint service delivers tangible benefits to stakeholders like the PWD. Its adaptability offers opportunities for other organizations to adopt similar solutions, ensuring broader applicability and long-term impact in ITS equipment management. Furthermore, the service could be effectively extended to other member states operating platforms similar to GNOSIS, facilitating compliance with the requirements of ITS directives.

Future Work

As part of continuous development and recognizing the significance of ongoing system support, certain crucial aspects should be addressed. One key area is the need to assess the efficiency of the desktop application in incorporating functionalities from the GNOSIS platform. By doing so, the system can support new capabilities,

improving overall performance and reliability. The system will be integrated with the existing ITS infrastructure, enabling real-time data exchange and centralized management of field assets. It will connect with the Traffic Management Center, SCADA systems, and GIS platforms via standardized APIs and gateways. This integration will allow automatic creation of maintenance tasks based on sensor alerts or equipment diagnostics. Maintenance activities and asset data will also be synchronized with the city's GIS and mobility dashboards, ensuring operational continuity and enhanced situational awareness across all ITS components. Machine learning tools can play a pivotal role in this evolution, analyzing data to uncover hidden patterns and correlations in reports while providing actionable recommendations for predictive maintenance. For example, AI models can analyze historical and real-time data to forecast sensor failures and monitor their health. Anomaly detection techniques further enhance accuracy by distinguishing between genuine environmental irregularities and sensor malfunctions. Automated diagnostics streamline fault classification and root cause analysis, enabling faster and more effective resolutions. Additionally, decision support systems powered by predictive models can prioritize maintenance tasks, offering guidance on whether to repair or replace sensors based on cost and criticality. Furthermore, AI-driven optimization of maintenance schedules enables condition-based maintenance, reducing unnecessary interventions and resource usage. By incorporating these advanced capabilities, the system can achieve greater efficiency and reliability while supporting a forward-looking approach to maintenance and system performance.

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